

DIDACTIC GAMES – THE MOST EFFECTIVE METHOD OF TEACHING PRIMARY EDUCATION SUBJECTS

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Annotatsiya

Boshlang'ich sinflarda ta'lim samaradorligini, o'quv predmetlarining ta'lim-tarbiyaviy va amaliy ahamiyatini oshirishda, o'quvchilarning o'quv predmetlarini o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini uyg'otishda didaktik o'yinlardan foydalanish haqida.

Тайанч so'zlar

mustaqil fikrlash, ijodiy fikrlash, tafakkurni rivojlantirish, amaliy ko'nikma, malaka, mantiqiy-ijodiy tafakkurni rivojlantirish, kommunikativ savodxonlikni oshirish.

Аннотация

Об использовании дидактических игр для повышения учебной эффективности, учебной и практической значимости учебных предметов в начальных классах, а также для пробуждения интереса учащихся к изучению учебных предметов.

Ключевые слова

самостоятельное мышление, творческое мышление, развитие мышления, практические навыки, компетентность, развитие логико-творческого мышления, повышение коммуникативной грамотности.

Abstract

On the use of didactic games to increase educational effectiveness, educational and practical significance of educational subjects in primary grades, as well as to awaken students' interest in studying academic subjects.

Key words

independent thinking, creative thinking, development of thinking, practical skills, competence, development of logical and creative thinking, increasing communicative literacy.

In order to improve the quality of education in our country and its widespread promotion, various pedagogical technologies are used today in the educational process. This means approaching the learning process with new innovations. The main goal is to make the lesson meaningful in all respects and increase the interest of children. Information and communication technologies and pedagogical

technologies are used in teaching primary school students in order to improve children's knowledge, expand their worldview, and quickly and easily master the lesson process.

Our state pays great attention to the field of education, the development of students' intellectual potential, independent and creative thinking skills, the ability to apply acquired knowledge in practice, practical skills and qualifications. To achieve these tasks, an important place in state educational policy is occupied by the need to effectively use all the possibilities of the educational process, pedagogical technologies and information technologies, didactic tools and methods.

The main goal of teaching subjects in primary education is to develop the skills of correct, accurate, expedient and effective use of language capabilities; development of logical and creative thinking, increasing communication literacy; formation of oriental education; it lies in the spiritual enrichment of the student's personality. In particular, on February 7, 2017, by the Decree of our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "On the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan," five priority areas for the development of our country for 2017-2021 were identified. Its fourth direction is called: "Development of the social sphere." In this direction, it is planned to implement measures to improve the quality of education and its development [1].

Primary education is an important stage in raising the mature generation. Therefore, attention to primary education and a new approach are one of the tasks that are the focus of public education. The effectiveness of developing writing skills in elementary school uniquely depends on the level of development of students' educational activities. Such activities are taught in the process of acquiring theoretical knowledge, under the guidance of a teacher and are developed regularly.

The concept of primary education emphasizes that students' learning depends on the extent to which they master reading and writing skills. If, during the initial education, a student acquires the ability to read quickly and consciously, has good writing skills, and a high level of literacy, he will definitely become an excellent student and a talented student in high school.

Today, raising a mature, proactive, responsible person in all respects is one of the important tasks of every subject teacher. Primary education is the foundation of personal education. It is important to achieve our goal of educating children of primary school age. The effectiveness of teaching is the main criterion for a teacher's work. Effectiveness is reflected in student engagement and mastery of

science. Didactic games are of particular importance in organizing the mental and motor activity of students during the period of primary education. At the same time, when teaching primary school students, it is necessary to effectively use various teaching methods. When a child goes to first school, you can observe that he becomes more playful and gets bored easily. Game-based learning technologies are aimed at making students active participants in the educational process without boring them.

In the elementary grades, as well as in later stages of education, this can be a great incentive to develop students' enthusiasm for knowledge. Such games have an effective effect on increasing the cognitive abilities of especially difficult-to-learn students. It should be noted that in textbooks created for primary grades, there is a noticeable lack of materials in this area.

It is important to increase the effectiveness of teaching in primary grades, the educational and practical significance of academic subjects, to arouse students' interest in studying academic subjects, and to introduce students to other methodological issues. One of the possibilities for a positive solution to this problem is the effective use of didactic games in the classroom. Therefore, the role of didactic games in creating motives in primary education is incomparable [2].

A didactic game is a spark that arouses enthusiasm and interest in learning among students. An educational game is a method used by adults - teachers, educators, parents - to develop certain qualities in primary school students. With the help of a didactic game, the process of acquiring knowledge by schoolchildren becomes easier, they learn to engage in various subjects, and they also develop a culture of behavior. The child's personality is formed through didactic play, in which mental characteristics associated with the organization of educational and work activities and entering into relationships with people in the future are formed.

Through didactic play, children learn about existence and try to change the world. Thus, the game lays the foundation for the formation of human activity. In a didactic game, a person demonstrates the ability to reflect existence. The most important significance of didactic play is that for the first time the child develops and develops the need to influence the world.

The gaming activities of students are of interest to scientists in many fields, that is, philosophers, sociologists, biologists, art historians, ethnographers, especially teachers and psychologists.

In psychology, play is considered a decisive factor in the development of a child's psyche. All aspects of a child's personality are formed in unity and interaction only in play. Didactic play creates an important basis for the transition

to a higher level of development of the child's psyche.

A didactic game is an active activity in the field of creating a simulation model of the events and phenomena being studied. The main difference between a game and other types of activities is that its subject is human activity. The main activity in the didactic game is joint learning activities. In a didactic game, it is important to have learning tasks that take into account the students' skills. When leading adults create some form of educational games, they should pay attention to those types that are interesting to children and attract their attention.

The traditions of widespread use of didactic games in teaching and raising children, established in folk pedagogy, were developed in the practical experience of teachers and the works of scientists.

The Czech teacher J. A. Komensky emphasized that play is the main form of child activity, and said that play corresponds to the character and interests of the child. The scientist emphasizes that the game comprehensively develops the child's mental abilities, expands his understanding of the environment, and develops his speech. In addition, playing together with peers brings him closer to his peers.

In raising children, didactic games are used in two directions: for the formation of a comprehensively developed personality and for narrow didactic purposes. The game is the main form of student activity. Didactic game is one of the important mental activities, during which all types of student's abilities develop, his understanding of the world around him expands, and the richness of speech increases. Didactic games have an effective impact on the development of various abilities, perception, speech and attention of the student [3].

Didactic games can be divided into three types: verbal, verbal, educational games, exercise games (actions). For didactic games, the game idea and game tasks are important. The most important element of a didactic game is its rule. In the process of fulfilling the rule, the content of the game is realized. The existence of a rule helps to realize the game effect and the application of the game task. In the process of following the rules, the worldview of the implementation of the game content is formed.

In a didactic game, the student learns to follow the rules. Because following the rules ensures the success of the game. In the process of participating in the game, positive moral qualities and organizational abilities are formed. Depending on the types of material used, didactic games can be divided into three types: games with objects, games on the table, and verbal games with words.

Object games are folk didactic toys, games using various natural mosaic materials. With their help, the teacher determines the types of games. For example,

by creating an entire landscape from pieces of natural material, games on the table serve to expand the understanding of the environment, interest students in knowledge, and develop thought processes (analysis, synthesis, generalization, classification, etc.). There are several types of board games: matching pictures, lotto, dominoes, cut out pictures and dice.

A play on words. This group of games includes very large folk games, namely "Chain", "Wrong Sentence", "It Can't Be", "Say Quickly", "Riddles", "Conversations", etc. This group of games includes games related to oral speech. .

Such games develop attention and memory, teach students to collect their thoughts, think quickly, connect speech, and think logically. A child acquires good moral qualities in didactic games. Didactic games are divided into several stages. At each stage, certain capabilities of the child are revealed.

The teacher's knowledge of the nature of these stages is of great importance in determining the effectiveness of didactic games.

At the first stage, the child has a desire to play and begins to be active in the game. At this stage, in order to interest the child in the game, you can organize riddles, tongue twisters, sayings or conversations.

At the second stage, the child learns to perform game tasks, follow the rules and participate in the game. At this stage, children develop positive qualities, such as correctness, the desire to achieve a goal, willpower, the ability to overcome even losses in a game, and joy not only in their own successes, but also in the successes of their friends. .

At the third stage of the didactic game, the child knows the rules of the game well. Now he approaches the game creatively, makes news himself, and is in demand on his own. During the game, he performs tasks such as finding quick answers, hiding, searching, running, describing, and so on. Each stage of the didactic game includes certain pedagogical tasks.

At the first stage of the didactic game, the teacher interests the children in the game, instills in them a good mood and a desire to look forward to new games.

At the second stage, he acts not as an observer, but as a participant in the game.

At the third stage of the didactic game, the teacher evaluates the creative abilities and activity of children during the game.

Didactic games are the most correct and effective method of teaching students independent thinking. It does not require specific materials or conditions, but it does require the knowledge and skills of the teacher in the field of organizing the game. Only the organization of a didactic game based on a specific system and

methodology plays an important role in developing students' ability to think independently. Didactic gaming activity is based on the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities of students during the educational process, and only then can students find effective game solutions and show relevance to themselves and others. Using games as a form of teaching requires the teacher to have confidence and skill in using the game.

Didactic games perform several tasks:

- educational, educational (impacts on the student's personality, develops his thinking, expands his worldview);
- applicability (the ability to apply knowledge to perform any educational tasks in a specific situation);
- stimulating motivation, increasing curiosity (interests students in cognitive activities, encourages them, promotes the development of cognitive interest).

Awakening students' interest in knowledge through didactic games is effective if it is organized based on their interests. In such cases, the child always has a desire to learn news and an interest in knowledge. Regular development and increased interest in knowledge fosters a positive attitude towards learning in younger schoolchildren and increases the level of mastery. Curiosity teaches a primary school student to search; he always learns to look for answers to various questions [4].

The student's curiosity develops in him a sense of emotional uplift and joy of success. Interest in learning not only has a positive effect on the outcome of the educational process, but also affects the active development of mental processes such as thinking, perception, memory and attention.

Interest in learning is one of the motives that increases students' interest in reading. His influence will be very strong. Encouraging curiosity can help even slow learners be productive. If students' activities and learning activities are systematically and regularly organized in a properly organized pedagogical process, interest in learning becomes one of the main qualities of the student's personality and has a strong influence on his development. Interest in knowledge becomes a powerful tool in the educational process. Abu Rayan Beruni emphasized that an important task is to interest students in the educational process, and in his book "Memorials of Ancient Peoples" he wrote: "The goal is not to prolong the sentence, but also not to tire the student, because constantly looking at the same thing leads to boredom and impatience. When a student walks through Fandanfan, it seems as if he is walking through different gardens. Before one can be seen, another begins, and he is interested in seeing them, and he wants to look at them,

because they say that everything has its own taste. “The same thing tires you, dulls your memory,” he said. Without activating a student’s cognitive activity, it is impossible to interest him in knowledge [5].

In short, the most important means of formative learning is to maintain the student's interest in knowledge and develop his motivation to learn during the educational process. Thus, interest in learning helps to realize all the potential of the student’s personality. Teaching children to play has a specific educational purpose. This is the most important meaning of the game. The didactic game differs from other types of teaching in the forms and methods of its implementation. The didactic game is aimed at achieving specific educational goals, that is, identifying, consolidating and deepening the studied material. During each didactic game, a specific goal is taken as a task, for example, consolidation of an action, a method of calculation, that is, a specific didactic task. This will greatly help in achieving the effectiveness of education.

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